

AGE DETECTION USING FACIAL IMAGE

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APPROVAL

This Thesis titled “Age Detection Using Facial Image”, submitted by Md. Mehedi Hassan and Md. Mahfuzur Rahman to the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Daffodil International University, has been accepted as satisfactory for the partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of B.Sc. in Computer Science and Engineering and approved as to its style and contents. The presentation has been held on 14 May 2022.

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We hereby declare that this project has been done by us under the supervision of **Dr. Md. Tarek Habib, Assistant Professor, Department of CSE** Daffodil International University. We also declare that neither this project nor any part of this project has been submitted elsewhere for award of any degree or diploma.

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ABSTRACT

This paper demonstrated using a number of methodologies to establish an age based on their face. There are numerous patterns hidden in the human face that can be used to confirm age estimates. Age determination is a method for detecting the age group and attempting to identify the precise age. The most difficult aspect of our approach was applying deep learning to convert data from images. Another difficulty was that people of the same age were divided into various age groups. One of the reasons for human face variation is the shape of the face. People appear diverse due to their lifestyles, environmental influences, and even various facial expressions. We have studied a number of articles on determining age from images in this paper. We tried to figure out what they did and how we could do something different. We worked by sharing the photos with nine different age groups. Following that, we employed CNN, VGG19, and RESNET methods. We are different from those who have studied in this field before us since we have employed more data and a variety of methodologies. CNN has an accuracy rate of 88.14%(RSMProp) and 85.47% (Adam), VGG19 has an accuracy rate of 88.24 %, and RESNET has an accuracy rate of 82.63 %.VGG 19 has a higher rate of accuracy. This is a better level of accuracy than other papers.

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PLAGIARISM REPORT

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CHAPTER 1

Introduction

1.1 Introduction

At present, many researchers around the world are working on determining age from pictures. Because of the wide consumption of age detection in several areas in recent years, there seems to be a huge interest in it.

Therefore, researchers are currently conducting research in line with science. The fast advancement of science and technology has benefited mankind in a variety of ways. At the same time, there has been an increase in interest in age estimates.

Artificial intelligence generally includes the field of estimation of age. In this field, age can be determined in different ways. Such as fingerprints, eye iris, mouth sounds. When it comes to establishing age, appearance is important. Because in all other cases that person will need to know the age of a person. In this scenario, simply possessing a human face is sufficient.

A large amount of study has been done on this topic during the last few decades.

There is no way to approach the same face twice. This is because numerous factors such as stance, facial expression, illumination, mustache, makeup, and haircut cause the appearance of the face to vary more frequently. Differences in face features result from such reasons. A person's face at one age differs from someone else's face at another age. Recent age guesstimates have spawned a slew of smaller platforms where Internet access control and alcohol machine resistance, and more.

The face is the most sensitive aspect of the human body. A person's age, gender, identity, race, and mood are all discernible from their face. Face image for age estimation has been a research issue of interest since the face provides crucial characteristics like age, gender, and identity.

So here we have chosen the image of the face to determine the age. Because so far it has not been possible to determine the exact age from the facial images. Despite the fact that numerous

researchers are working on this. One by one, people are trying to figure out how to determine age from pictures. However, they are unable to discover a suitable answer.

The lack of an accurate image database with age information was the primary impediment to one researcher's investigation [1]. They took 498 digital photos of persons ranging in age from 1 to 85 who were members of a group. Four age groups are chosen using their proposed algorithm. The age groups are 0-15, 18-30, 31-50, and over 51 years old. They used 296 photographs for training and 200 for testing. Their evaluated photos, here on the other side, had a detection accuracy of 86.64 percent.

They tested with 114 photos in which diffuse frontiers, dark areas, and other wrinkle-like characteristics fooled the algorithm [4]. Furthermore, the user database is not as large as it may be, which limits the study. Certainly, the outcomes of the trials would be better if the database was larger.

The face photos are grouped into three age groups here [2]. There are three age groups: 10-30 years, 30-50 years, and above 50 years. Biometric ratio and wrinkle analysis are used to determine face characteristics. Three distinct categories were predicted using algorithms. Furthermore, the findings are verified using a suitably big database.

They operate with age categorization for the first time [13]. The grayscale face picture was separated into three age ranges. However, because they employed a tiny dataset at the time, their approach is no longer useful.

They discovered a weakness in [13]'s work and then developed a plan to correct it [14]. However, in their own minds, they have separated the pictures of the faces one by one. It's possible that assuming their age isn't the best idea here.

The ages were separated as follows: 0-2 years for children, 3-39 years for younger children, 40-59 years for middle-aged people, and 60-100 years for adults. However, such a categorization is not acceptable at the moment.

We found a slew of papers on age identification using previously published facial images. So, in our research paper, we explored something new and wanted to show the actual age or a range very near to the age from the image of the face in a somewhat more precise method.

The main focus of our research is on recognizing various types of age detection.

We used Kaggle, Google, and our surroundings to acquire information on various stage facial photos. After obtaining raw data, we preprocess it. Deep learning algorithms play a critical role in determining age through picture categorization. A variety of deep learning algorithms can be used to predict age based on various criteria. This research is analyzed using four three different deep learning algorithms. VGG19, CNN and Resnet are the three. We used around 13300 pieces of data to train the algorithms that make up the recommended framework. Following that, we identified our ideal algorithm, which helps us to attain our goal. As a consequence, age detection diagnosis will be easy, and this will be our accomplishment.

1.2 Motivation

Every day, the world improves for the benefit of science. Every day new things are being discovered. Similarly, it is now possible to determine a person's age, gender, and more using biometrics using artificial intelligence. However, their physical presence must be confirmed. However, doing so in all places can be tough. If a picture of a man's face can be used to guess his age. The age of that guy can be simply determined, and favorable results will follow for everyone in all circumstances. For example, in the case of school-college admissions, if the exact age of a student is determined through a photograph of a student without using various means of biometrics, then this method will be good for everyone. Those are all the reasons we were motivated.

1.3 Rationale of the Study

Admittedly, there has been a lot of study on this topic of face recognition. Some of this research could come from a giant company. Large organizations may be undertaking these studies for their own purposes. However, the majority of the research was conducted with a little amount of data or with a limited number of methods. Moreover, more data and procedures must be used in order to achieve substantial progress in this research; otherwise, the outputs will be erroneous. Determining age from the face is a necessary stage in this age of information technology, as well as the way the world is developing. All of this entices us to conduct research.

1.4 Expected Outcome

Our first and foremost goal is to publish this research paper in a journal. And the goal is to be able to estimate or calculate an individual's age from a photo of a facial image.

1.5 Report Layout

Here each chapter is examined from a variety of viewpoints, and each chapter contains numerous components that are thoroughly covered. The contents of this report are as follows:

Chapter 1: Introduction

Here, we discussed determining a user's age from a face photograph. Our thesis's introduction, motivation, study rationale, and projected conclusion were all presented.

Chapter 2: Background

We talk about the conditions surrounding our thesis. We've worked on three different models here. We discussed their principal ailment. We also discussed the related works and summary of the research.

Chapter 3: Research methodology

We discussed the methodology of this thesis in detail in this chapter. We also discussed the search topic and instruments, data gathering procedures, statistical analysis, and implementation needs at this time.

Chapter 4: Experimental results and discussion

Here, We reviewed the experiment's outcome as well as a deep analysis of the whole procedure. We talked in detail about the experimental results, descriptive analysis of our experiment and summary of the experiment.

Chapter 5: Summary, Conclusion, recommendation, and implication for future research

Here we explored the social influence on our society in this chapter. Society's Impact, Ethical Issues, and a Long-Term Plan

Chapter 6: Summary, Conclusion, Recommendation & Implication for Future Research

The final concepts of the project are discussed in this chapter. This chapter is in charge of displaying the entire project report in accordance with suggestions. We also talked about the study's summary, conclusion, and implications for future research.

CHAPTER 2

Background

2.1 Introduction

The face seems to be the most valuable component of the body. Because the face communicates crucial data like age, gender, and identity. Using facial images to estimate age has become a prominent research topic. Basically, we started our research by reading reviews of relevant literature. Our study focuses on detecting age from facial data. We apply three different types of machine learning algorithms and some different types of optimizer to build the framework we need. The items are VGG19, CNN, and Resnet. The face seems to be the most valuable component of the body. Because the face communicates crucial data like age, gender, and identity.

2.2 Related Works

(M.M. Dehshibi and A. Bastanfard, 2010.) This paper provides a new, rapid, flexible, and efficient age group detection technique based on frontal facial images[1]. Some of the findings in this field include facial recognition system [10], face expression [11], gender classification [12], detection and face recognition and facial feature extraction [12]. Age-related research has been looked at from two angles. Facial aging classification [5] (To construct a system that can predict the age of a particular face in an image, training and test sets are used.) Facial aging simulation [19]. (The second category simulates aging effects, allowing users to create age-progressed or age-regressed images of themselves.) Because of the IFDB's vastness, this technique has been shown to be beneficial. Although the IFDB is limited to the Caucasian race, it will be applicable to multiple generations because it employs ratios of facial feature points rather than their distance. The rate of accuracy is 86.64 percent.

(Alonso, J.B., V. Almeida, M.K. Dutta, C.M. Travieso, A. Singh, and V. Almeida, 2016) An old-school biometric system was used in this essay [4]. This system uses a categorization mechanism as well as preprocessing parameterization. The FG-NET Aging Database was used, which contains 1,002 face images from 82 Caucasian descent subjects, each labeled with their age, and the database "Adience benchmark of unfiltered faces for gender and age categorization," which

contains 26,580 images from 2,284 persons representing diverse ethnic groups, resulting in a total of 26,580 age groupings. The photographs were then grayscale, equalized, and scaled to 92x112 pixels. The prediction is correct 86.64 percent of the time.

(R. Angulu, J.R. Tapamo, and A.O. Adewumi, 2018) A face is represented by a set of form and texture properties extracted from a facial image [3]. Because model parameters encode both facial shape and texture, AAM can display both young and aged faces. AAM is frequently used in conjunction with regression-based age estimation approaches. Gallagher's FG-NET, MORPH, and web-collected Gallagher's databases are all available.

A Microsoft software called How old do I appear to be was produced. [9], which gets good results in age prediction based on the image, however it is not without errors.

Two more websites, Online Age Detector [10] and Kairos [11] claim to have systems that can estimate age or age ranges based on facial photographs and video images, respectively. Both admit that the results of these applications aren't totally trustworthy.

Face.com [12], an Israeli company that provides facial recognition to various websites and corporations, including Facebook, which bought it in 2012 after testing its services, has an application that attempts to calculate a person's age by analyzing their face.

(Ingole, A.L. and Karande, K.J., 2018) The Viola Jones algorithm is used to determine age biometrically, and the support vector machine [SVM] is employed to extract Euclidean distance features [5]. Using trial and error methods, the whole data is compiled from different person-to-person FFE databases. To classify the system's stream, the first mode data is employed. In trial mode, SVM is utilized to find the output.

To establish the age, a database is generated with a total of 90 photographs divided into six groups. There are 15 photographs in each set.

Grayscale face photos were separated into three age groups by Kwon and Lobo [13]. There are fewer than 68 percent of newborns who are identified. Their method is inefficient for real-time processing due to the use of energy functions. To test their method, the researchers examined a small sample of wrinkle images (47 high-resolution shots). Due to the tiny database, effective evaluation of the results was challenging.

[14] Horng et al. They classified the 230 photos into four categories based on their age. Defects can be found, despite the fact that their technology claims a recognition rate of 81.58 percent for test images. For starters, the age of the facial image in the test set is given subjectively, therefore the age estimation could be incorrect. They also have an algorithm.

Hayashi and colleagues divided people's ages into ten-year intervals. They start by removing skin portions from photographs of people's faces. Finally, the age and the gender lookup table are created. Despite using a consistent age range for classification, their age estimation method was only 27% accurate in 300 pictures. Despite the fact that major facial changes do not occur until the age of 15, the marketing approach for the "15 and under" age group is disregarded.

According to Lanitis et al, The "age estimation methods" age group is underserved in their marketing approach. They developed an aging function to show the aging process. During the study, a quadratic age function for each person was generated.

Kalamani et al. -> A fuzzy lattice neural network was used to construct an age categorization system.

Qi and Zhang -> presented an automatic age categorization system that distinguishes between online child and adult faces. The system's three components are facial recognition, face alignment and normalization, and age categorization. ICA extracts statistically independent bases from images that contain local facial components in the first stage. A selection of fundamental pictures is then chosen based on mutual understanding and class labels. An SVM classifier was used in the final stage. A two-age-group classification paradigm is presented in this study. Because of the utilization of ICA features, the proposed approach cannot be generalized to other races.

2.3 Summary of Research

The goal of this study is to use deep learning techniques to determine age from face data. We established an effective approach for determining age. To collect data, we use Google and some open-source internet. We utilized 13300 images as data to generate this model. Because it is more dynamically modified by a range of characteristics, the face was chosen. After the data was obtained, we preprocessed it. As part of the preprocessing process, we clean datasets, restructure data, and so on. To train and test our data, we use three deep learning techniques: VGG19, CNN, Resnet. Then we obtain the outcome we want.

CHAPTER 3

Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

We used some techniques in our research, just as we would in any other study. We tried to include some creativity from those who had previously conducted research on this topic. We'll go over the beginning and end of our project in detail in the following sections.

We gathered information from various accessible Google and Internet sources before sorting it. Data clearing, data resizing, data augmentation has been done in pre-processing. In the following future extraction, we completed data training and testing. We used Deep Learning as a method to advance our work, as well as CNN, VGG19, and RESNET to establish the classification outcome.

Figure 3.1.1: Working Procedure.

3.2 Research Subject and Instrumentation

Age Detection Using Facial Image is the title of our thesis proposal. Age detection is a major area in the study right now. We employed certain deep learning models in our study technique since we used some mathematical functions in our proposed model. Working with a deep learning model will be incredibly challenging for us because it needs a high-configuration PC, GPU, and other equipment. The equipment and technologies required to get our model up and running are listed below -

Hardware and Software:

- 8GB RAM and Intel Core i5 8th generation processor.
- 1TB hard drive.
- GPU-powered Google Colab

Tools for Development:

- Windows 11 is the latest version of Windows.
- Python 3.7.13 is required.
- TensorFlow version 2.8.0

Backend

NumPy.

- Pandas.

3.3 Data Collection Procedure

The systematic gathering and computation of data-related variables is known as data collection. Although most of the scholars use data from internet sites. We also used the online platform for the majority of the data. At the same time, we've acquired some data from ourselves and others.

We categorize and label the data after it is collected. To execute our experiments, we collect three sorts of data. The training dataset is one, the validation dataset is one, while the tested dataset is the other.

Our collection is mainly composed of natural images. We begin by processing the picture that was gathered. Then we turn it into data. Then we put three algorithms in place to achieve our aim.

3.4 Statistical Analysis

We took 13300 photos of people of all ages for our experiment. We've separated them into nine different groups.

Out of a total of 13300 data, we used 60% data (8000 data) for training and 10% data (1300 data) for testing and 30% data (4000 data) for validation. The nine age groups that we have classified into age groups are as follows: age 1 (0-2), age 2 (3-6), age 3 (7-12), age 4 (13-19), age 5 (20-30), age 6 (31-45), age 7 (46-60), age 8 (61-75), age 9 (76-100).

Figure 3.4.1: Categories of ages.

We gathered data regarding different age categories in our dataset. A graph of data partitioning by age is shown below.

Figure 3.4.2: Ratio of Data Split.

Table 3.4.1 Total of all different ages

Group of age	Total Data	Testing Dataset	Training Dataset	Validation Dataset
Age 1 (0 years-2years)	1567	100	987	480
Age 2 (3years-7years)	1599	180	964	455
Age 3 (8years-12years)	1191	140	703	348
Age 4 (13years-19years)	1418	145	908	365
Age 5 (20years-30years)	1561	160	974	427
Age 6 (31years-45years)	1740	180	1008	552
Age 7 (46years-60years)	1607	119	971	517
Age 8 (60-years-75years)	1552	111	973	468
Age 9 (76years-100years)	1021	120	514	387

Observed Category Of Testing Dataset

Figure 3.4.3: Identified testing dataset category

Observed Category Of Training Dataset

Figure 3.4.4: Identified training dataset category

Observed Category Of Validation Dataset

Figure 3.4.5: Identified Validation dataset category

3.5 Proposed Methodology

The process for determining a person's age. Each image in the input image collection is put into consideration. The approach is based on the face's overall size. The primary features of a person's facial expression can be utilized to estimate their age. The size of the face grows larger with age and takes on an extended form. It has been scientifically proven.

There are several sorts of algorithms, models, and strategies for various types of motives in deep learning. As a result, our provided approach requires deep learning. VGG19, Convolution Neural Network, and Resnet were the three main models we tested. It will also be quite valuable for our suggested project.

Figure 3.5.1: Our Proposed Method's Architecture.

3.5.a VGG19

The VGG-19 network has 19 layers and is a deep convolutional network. VGG-19 is a form of neural network that used ImageNet to produce over million pictures. The image component is loaded to preprocess the picture object, and the pre-processing input module is exported to scale pixel values suitably for such a VGG19 model. Arrays are processed using the NumPy module. The VGG19 model is then fed the pre-trained weights for the ImageNet dataset. In the VGG19 model, a convolution step is represented by one or more dense (or totally coupled) levels.

Figure 3.5.a.1: Architecture of VGG19.[24]

- i) The input to this network was a fixed-size ($224 * 224$) RGB image, meaning that the matrix was of structure $(224,224,3)$.
- ii) The only preprocessing included removing the standard RGB value from every pixel, which was calculated over the whole training dataset.
- iii) To cover the complete visual notion, they employed kernels with a size of $(3 * 3)$ and a stride length of 1 pixel.
- vi) Max-pooling was done using side 2 across a $2 * 2$ -pixel window.

Figure 3.5.a.2: VGG19 model layer. [7]

3.5.b Convolutional Neural Network(CNN)

When compared to a fully connected neural network, CNN offers distinct benefits in picture identification. A conventional CNN structure includes four different kinds of neuronal layers: convolution layers, pooling layer, smoothing layer, and then fully connected layer.[35]. Figure 3.5.b.1 depicts a typical CNN for image categorization.

Figure 3.5.b.1: CNN for image recognition flowchart. [15]

An image is defined as an array of image pixels with the dimensions $h \times w \times d$, where h and w correspond to the pixel values inside the heights and widths orientations, respectively, and where d counts the set of color data, which in a normal color of RGB image, this equals three. By compressing the input image, the convolution technique takes information from it. In a convolutional layer, each similar filter is a tiny matrix with the dimensions $f_h \times f_w \times d$. Despite the fact that f_h and f_w are frequently smaller than h and w , the depth of the training image matrix and the filtering matrix will be the same. Each filter in a convolution layer convolves an input image

whenever it goes through it, resulting in a small transformation matrix called a "feature map. After all of the filters have finished their convolutions, the input image is transformed into a small matrix with more depth. The amount of filters in the convolution layers is connected to the depth, which must be selected by that the user prior to image analysis. Figure 3.5.b.2 illustrates a sketch map of the array of matrix convolution with such a single filter, having a stride of one. The created feature map is then exposed to nonlinear process using a nonlinear function after convolution. Because of its quicker calculation and lack of need for unsupervised pre-training [25], For non-linear mapping, the rectified linear unit is often employed in CNN. [24]. $f(x)=\max(0,x)$ is how the ReLU function is expressed:

Figure 3.5.b.2: A single filter does the convolution. [16]

The pooling layer's goal is to conserve important data while shrinking the size of extracted features obtained from the convolution layers. In reality, Maximum pooling, batch normalization, and total pooling are three distinct pooling methods used by CNN. [19]. The max-pooling approach is used to find the greatest number from the corrected convolution layer. (with a stride of two)(see Figure 3). Max-pooling can decrease image size even further without preserving vital info. The convolution and pooling layers of a CNN might be merged numerous times determined by the size of the source image.

Figure 3.5.b.3: A single filter does the convolution. [17]

After all convolution layers and average pooling have been applied in the proposed image, The matrix formed by the last pooling layer is straightened by a smoothing level, resulting in a lengthy vector. The ultimate recognition result is obtained by feeding this vector into a fully connected neural network.

3.5.c ResNet

ResNets (Residual Networks) is another name for ResNets. ResNet is a kind of CNN that is used in image recognition. ResNet's first application was Deep Residual Learning for Image Processing.

ResNets of various depths, such as ResNet-50 and ResNet-152, can be constructed. The number at the end of ResNet indicates how many layers or how deep the networks are. ResNet-50 was our choice. ResNet-50 is a deep convolutional neural network with 50 layers. Using the basic building pieces of a ResNet that we will be discussing, we may develop a ResNet with any depth:

The skip connections employed in ResNets may be seen as an enhanced version of the VGG design. The architecture of the VGG, as well as the 34 layer ResNet, may be shown in the diagram below.

Figure 3.5.c.1:Architecture of ResNet. [40]

3.6 Implementation Requirements

There are various alternatives and types of models for different sorts of motives in deep learning. We applied three models in our proposed project. These three models are quite effective for determining age from a face image. Our datasets mostly consist of human face photos obtained from Kaggle and Google. This model works by categorizing images through machines and identifying images of ages with the highest level of accuracy, from which we obtain our final result.

CHAPTER 4

Experimental Results And Discussion

4.1 Introduction

We'll go over the several algorithms used in this project before moving on to this part. The outcomes of the algorithms utilized in this study will be discussed in this chapter. Before I go any further, I'd want to point out that the majority of our work focuses on Deep Learning. For image categorization, we employed VGG19, CNN, and ResNet. The output of our models, as well as the testing of other outcomes, will be described in this section. The model's optimization and loss were reduced using two optimizers: Adam and RMSProp. It may be able to provide us with good accuracy after training data. For the training phase, Adam optimizer is the most important of the others.

Deep learning algorithm model training needs a good setup PC or laptop. A Global Processing Unit is required while training datasets. To get started, we'll use a direct PC to train our proposed model. As a result, the model takes longer to execute, perhaps resulting in incorrect findings. To train our models for this project, we use Google Colab. This project required the usage of Google Colab to train our models.

4.2 Descriptive Analysis

The validity of a deep learning classification system may be estimated using a confusion matrix. To display how many instances have been allocated to each class.

Accuracy: It refers to the model's percentage of true predictions.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \text{Correct Predictions} / \text{Total Prediction}$$

Precision: First and foremost, please inform us of the importance of precision. It is the proportion of true positives to the true total of genuine positive pulse false positives. The proportion of actual results out of all positive predictions made by the model. It's mostly utilized for retrieving information. This is how we can write.

$$\text{Precision} = (TP / (TP + FP)) \times 100\%$$

Recall: The ratio of true positive to true positive, false negative values is known as recall. It is a metric for determining the model's completeness.

$$\text{Recall} = (TP / (TP + FN)) \times 100\%$$

F1-score: A balance of recall and accuracy is characterized as the F1 score. The f1 score reflects both false positives and false negatives.

$$\text{F1-Score} = ((2 \times \text{precision} \times \text{recall}) / (\text{precision} + \text{recall})) \times 100\%$$

Table 4.2.1 Matrix calculation of Adam Optimizer

Class Name	Precision	Recall	Fi-score	Support
Age1	0.82	0.76	0.84	480
Age2	0.76	0.72	0.83	455
Age3	0.82	0.76	0.80	348
Age4	0.69	0.80	0.86	365
Age5	0.79	0.83	0.76	427
Age6	0.60	0.57	0.64	552
Age7	0.75	0.71	0.82	517
Age8	0.72	0.66	0.74	468
Age9	0.65	0.60	0.82	387

False Negative Rate (FNR): A false negative is when the model predicts the negative class inaccurately.

$$\text{False Negative Rate} = \text{False Negative} / (\text{False negative} + \text{True Positive}) \times 100\%$$

Negative Predictive Value (NPV): It's the percentage of persons who were really diagnosed as negative compared to the overall number of people who got negative test results.

$$\text{Negative Predictive Value} = \text{True Negative} / (\text{True Negative} + \text{False negative}) \times 100\%$$

False Discovery rate : The overall number of discoveries is subtracted from the total number of false discoveries.

$$\text{False Discovery rate} = \text{False Positive} / (\text{True Positive} + \text{False Positive}) \times 100\%$$

4.3 Experimental Results

The end outcome is a critical component of every endeavor. We are all aware that no machine is capable of giving 100% accurate results. The model we used for our project produced decent results, however, it wasn't always 100% correct. We use three distinct sorts of models and two different types of optimizers to reach the best results. VGG19, CNN, and the ResNet Model were used. Additionally, Adam and RMSProp optimizers were employed. Where the two optimizers yielded three distinct results. We achieved the best accuracy of 88.24 % on the InceptionV3 of the VGG19 model. Implementing an Adam optimizer yields the best results. Furthermore, by combining the CNN model with the RMSprop optimizer, we were able to reach a result of 88.14 % and 85.47% from Adam optimizer. We also use the ResNet model, which yields an accuracy of 82.63 %. Which of them was the worst.

Table 4.3.1: Test result of different models and optimizer

Model Name	Optimizer	Test Loss	Test Precision	Test Recall	Test Accuracy
VGG19	RMSProp	0.30	0.89	0.87	88.24%
CNN	Adam	0.39	0.86	0.84	85.47%
CNN	RMSprop	0.32	0.90	0.87	88.14%
ResNet	Adam	0.46	0.86	0.84	82.63%

4.3.1 VGG19

We get our best accuracy by using VGG19 model, among of three models. We got 88.24% accuracy. Table 4.3.1.1 displays the detailed result of the last 10 epochs. The testing set's loss, precision, recall, and accuracy are listed in the last four columns. Finally, we achieved 88.24% accuracy with 0.89 precision and 0.87 recall.

Table 4.3.1.1: Test and train result of VGG19 model with Adam Optimizer

Train Loss	Train Precision	Train Recall	Train Accuracy	Val Loss	Val Precision	Val Recall	Val Accuracy
0.4471	0.8410	0.8109	0.8278	0.3066	0.8924	0.8642	0.8792
0.4399	0.8406	0.8074	0.8249	0.3340	0.8769	0.8519	0.8646
0.4536	0.8420	0.8086	0.8259	0.3103	0.8857	0.8681	0.8772
0.4504	0.8375	0.8036	0.8222	0.3257	0.8831	0.8614	0.8717
0.4276	0.8476	0.8189	0.8352	0.2850	0.9005	0.8816	0.8919
0.4317	0.8462	0.8183	0.8330	0.2996	0.8909	0.8733	0.8840
0.4387	0.8403	0.8103	0.8258	0.3275	0.8897	0.8689	0.8792
0.4258	0.8452	0.8170	0.8325	0.2883	0.8972	0.8776	0.8859
0.4425	0.8412	0.8113	0.8270	0.2896	0.9095	0.8875	0.9006
0.4242	0.8465	0.8160	0.8326	0.2997	0.8930	0.8729	0.8824

Figure 4.3.1.1: The comparison between train and validation in terms of accuracy.

4.3.2 CNN

We get 85.47% accuracy from CNN model with Adam optimizer. Which is quite good, but slightly lower than RMSProp optimizer. 88.14% accuracy from RMSProp. This optimizer requires to achieve this accuracy. This is shown in table 4.3.2.1. In this table first four columns contain loss of train, Tr precision of train, recall of train , and accuracy of train, and another four columns contain test Loss, Test Precision, Test, Recall and test Accuracy. We achieved 88.14% test accuracy with 0.90 Test Precision and 0.87 test recall from RMSProp Optimizer .

Table 4.3.2.1.a: Test and train result of CNN model with RMSProp Optimizer

Train Loss	Train Precision	Train Recall	Train Accuracy	Val Loss	Val Precision	Val Recall	Val Accuracy
0.5143	0.8150	0.7678	0.7923	0.3876	0.8748	0.8455	0.8583
0.5238	0.8173	0.7661	0.7942	0.3581	0.8835	0.8575	0.8726
0.5145	0.8198	0.7664	0.7937	0.4540	0.8527	0.8248	0.8384
0.5028	0.8243	0.7776	0.8019	0.3638	0.8801	0.8535	0.8615
0.5049	0.8194	0.7738	0.8005	0.3809	0.8871	0.8511	0.8686
0.5048	0.8201	0.7743	0.8004	0.3638	0.8853	0.8607	0.8742
0.4838	0.8321	0.7891	0.8112	0.3439	0.8906	0.8686	0.8798
0.5013	0.8242	0.7777	0.8037	0.3741	0.8751	0.8535	0.8646
0.4906	0.8291	0.7827	0.8088	0.3437	0.8842	0.8694	0.8766
0.4935	0.8261	0.7791	0.8045	0.3213	0.8968	0.8718	0.8814

Figure 4.3.2.1.a: The comparison between train and validation in terms of accuracy, and loss

We achieved 85.47% test accuracy with 0.86 Test Precision and 0.84 test recall from Adam Optimizer .

Table 4.3.2.1.b: Test and train result of CNN model with Adam Optimizer

Train Loss	Train Precision	Train Recall	Train Accuracy	Val Loss	Val Precision	Val Recall	Val Accuracy
0.5340	0.8055	0.7569	0.7847	0.4198	0.8451	0.8127	0.8289
0.5273	0.8066	0.7580	0.7846	0.4130	0.8545	0.8166	0.8384
0.5172	0.8084	0.7659	0.7899	0.4132	0.8450	0.8139	0.8329
0.5280	0.8093	0.7637	0.7907	0.3876	0.8562	0.8301	0.8455
0.5248	0.8154	0.7691	0.7946	0.3737	0.8668	0.8400	0.8582
0.5115	0.8165	0.7727	0.7965	0.3932	0.8604	0.8325	0.8499
0.5015	0.8134	0.7745	0.7959	0.4054	0.8504	0.8218	0.8368
0.4979	0.8174	0.7759	0.8001	0.3960	0.8591	0.8285	0.8475
0.4957	0.8184	0.7811	0.8010	0.3907	0.8596	0.8269	0.8455
0.4906	0.8215	0.7818	0.8031	0.3869	0.8646	0.8420	0.8547

Figure 4.3.2.1.b: The comparison between train and validation in terms of accuracy, and loss

4.3.3 ResNet

By applying the ResNet Model with Adam optimizer we get 82.63 % accuracy, which is much less than the VGG19 and CNN model. As always, the first four columns contain loss of train, Train precision of train, recall of train, and accuracy of train and the last four columns contain the Test Loss, Test Precision, Test Recall and test Accuracy of this optimizer. After that, we get 82.63% accuracy, 0.85 test precision and 0.80 test recall.

Table 4.3.3.1: Test and train result of ResNet model with Adam Optimizer

Train Loss	Train Precision	Train Recall	Train Accuracy	Val Loss	Val Precision	Val Recall	Val Accuracy
0.6707	0.7571	0.6757	0.7530	0.5505	0.7970	0.7538	0.7777
0.6545	0.7610	0.6777	0.7521	0.5072	0.8207	0.7657	0.7936
0.6361	0.7706	0.6985	0.7536	0.4815	0.8194	0.7737	0.7968
0.6337	0.7725	0.7017	0.7622	0.5016	0.8138	0.7697	0.7928
0.6253	0.7745	0.7023	0.7601	0.4405	0.8342	0.7896	0.8135

0.6190	0.7780	0.7072	0.7639	0.4791	0.8282	0.7721	0.8016
0.6061	0.7795	0.7102	0.7744	0.4575	0.8326	0.8008	0.8159
0.6119	0.7751	0.7122	0.7727	0.4985	0.8267	0.7753	0.8024
0.6025	0.7845	0.7168	0.7760	0.4754	0.8411	0.8016	0.8191
0.5924	0.7849	0.7227	0.7773	0.4604	0.8480	0.8000	0.8263

Figure 4.3.3.1: The comparison between train and validation in terms of accuracy, and loss

4.4 Summary

Algorithms based on deep learning were used. We suggested three potential models for our project. Two optimizers were also employed. We measure all sorts of loss functions during the training stage and wait until all iterations are complete before computing the final loss function. Before beginning the model training, we separated the data into test groups and train groups.

CHAPTER 5

Impact on Society, Environment And Sustainability

5.1 Impact on Society:

The human face is made up of structural and texture features taken from an image of the face. The use of the face to estimate age will have a favorable social impact. We are currently living in an information technology era. In this new world, data is the most valuable asset. As a result, we are gradually entering the nanotechnology era. Determining the age of the face has become increasingly important in recent years. This issue is connected to a number of offices, organizations, and even government operations. Furthermore, there is a huge amount of online content that is unacceptable for people of all ages. In today's online world, there are numerous gaming-adult sites that kids are prohibited from entering. So, as technology advances, if we can use these tools to meet our own wants, our lives will have a far greater impact on society.

5.2 Ethical Aspects

In terms of morality, our work and manner do not threaten the privacy of any human being. Our paperwork does not break any of our civilized society's ethical standards. Also, don't do something that can endanger others in the future. We gathered our information from various internet sources, all of which are open source. We have not done anything to harm persons or society during our job. I am unable to make a claim. There is no way to assert any form of privacy. During our paperwork, we used our own computers and the internet. I've also never used anyone else's data or equipment. We did our research with integrity, legality, and transparency in mind.

5.3 Sustainability Plan

The main purpose was to determine age from facial photos. To ensure the quality of our work, we converted the image to data and then used the data to calculate the level of accuracy. To do this, we used a deep learning algorithm. In the course of our effort, we used almost 13300 photographs. Because we've dealt with such a vast amount of data, we can say that the future stability of our work is assured. Because we were able to determine the age from such a large number of images, any major corporation may choose to use our work without hesitation for future projects, improving the work's long-term viability. In this work, we'll employ more images and data.

CHAPTER 6

Conclusion and Future Work

6.1 Summary of the Study

In our study, we looked at guessing age from the faces of persons of various ages. It was not an easy journey to employment. It was a difficult task for us. For the previous four months, we've been collecting data and forming the structure. We've employed deep learning to help us work more efficiently. We believe that estimating age from images is a useful concept for everyone. Part by part, we completed our task. In general, we've tried to maintain a sense of consistency in our work. The ongoing aspects of our cause are also described below.

Step 1: Use Google and a few other freely available websites to get data.

Step 2: We have stored the data in different categories based on age.

Step 3: For accessibility and a huge amount of data, we chose Google Drive.

Step 4: We switched data from images to pre-processing data.

Step 5: Using methods. These are CNN, VGG19, and RESNET.

Step 6: Optimizers are Adam, RMSProp.

Step 7: We double-checked the results we received.

We have ensured the quality of our work by following the processes outlined above. At the same time, we are positive that our efforts will help people in the future.

6.2 Conclusion

We have worked on a paper that can determine age from human appearance. We have collected images of people of different ages from different mediums on the internet, most of which are open sources of the internet. The main purpose of our work is to make life easier for people in the future and to do research on security issues of different sites. As well as ensuring accuracy by processing the collected data through several algorithms. After that, we used CNN, VGG19, and RESNET methodologies. We differ from previous researchers in this topic since we have used more data and a range of methodologies. CNN has an 88.14%(RSMProp) and 85.47% (Adam) accuracy rate, VGG19 has an 88.24 % accuracy rate, and RESNET has an 82.63 % accuracy rate. Here, VGG19 has best accuracy . This paper has better accuracy than others.

6.3 Implication for Further Study

Almost everyone knows that a paper's work does not complete when it is finished. Of course, there are weaknesses and leaks in our work. We have taken the help of the internet without collecting data directly.

However, we believe that if we could get the data manually, we would be able to go deeper into the topic. We want to ensure progress in new ways in the future. We want to improve the quantity of data we have, and we want to work with more algorithms in the future to get better outcomes.

The appearance of a person's face differs from one person to another. Photographs of a single moment should not be used to determine the age. Human face expressions determine a lot. With expression, even the softness and hardness of the face can be manipulated. As a result, we'll try to work with human facial expressions in the future.

In addition, we will attempt to reflect on the work in the real world.

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Plagiarism Report

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